

1 **Fast determination of a new prototype Fe (III) chelate of benzenecetic acid, 2-**
2 **hydroxy- α -[(2-hydroxyethyl)amino] by liquid chromatography**

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26 **Abstract**

27 This study developed and validated an analytical method for determination of a new
28 prototype iron chelate – Fe(III)-benzeneacetate,2-hydroxy- α -[(2-hydroxyethyl)amino] –
29 (BHH/Fe³⁺) based on liquid chromatography with diode array detection.
30 Chromatographic analysis (3.5 min) was performed on a LiChrospher RP-18 (150 x
31 4.6 mm; particle size 5 μ m) in reversed phase mode, with a mobile phase consisting of a
32 sodium borate buffer 0.20 mM at pH=10 (solvent A) and acetonitrile (solvent B) at a flow
33 rate of 1.0 mL/min in isocratic elution mode. This method was fully validated and found
34 to be linear from the limit of detection (LOD) to 50 mg/L and precise (standard deviation
35 values below 5 %). The proposed method was demonstrated to be selective, precise and
36 robust. The limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) were 0.8 and 2.7 mg/L
37 respectively. The developed methodology indicated that it is suitable for the
38 quantification of iron chelate BHH/Fe³⁺.

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52 **Keywords:** (benzeneacetic acid, 2-hydroxy- α -[(2-hydroxyethyl)amino]); iron chelate;
53 fertilisers; liquid chromatography

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55 **1. Introduction**

56 Currently, the most effective method for curing iron deficiency in crops is the application
57 of iron fertilisers to soil or foliage. Iron fertilisers must comply with current EU
58 regulations EU2003/2003 (EU Directive, 2003, and subsequent amendments) and EU
59 1009/2019 [1-2]. EU 2003/2003 includes FeSO₄ as the only Fe²⁺ inorganic salt, synthetic
60 Fe³⁺-chelates, and a selected number of Fe complexes of low stability [1]. Inorganic salts
61 have low efficiency in neutral-basic soils due to their rapid precipitation, thus their use is
62 limited to low reactive media or foliar applications. Synthetic iron chelates, which are
63 widely used in agriculture, are products of medium-high stability using
64 polyaminocarboxylate chelating agents. Chelates are complex organic molecules in
65 which Fe³⁺ is surrounded by a coordination sphere formed by chelating agents such
66 organic anions that are able to donate electrons to the metal centre. This prevents metal
67 precipitation, and the iron remains in solution and is transported to the plant root [3-4].
68 Among the most commonly used chelating agents are ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid
69 (EDTA), ethylenediamine-N-N'bis(o-hydroxyphenylacetic) acid (*o,o*-EDDHA) and N-
70 N'bis(o-hydroxyphenyl) ethylenediamine-N-N'-diacetic acid (HBED) with medium to
71 high affinity to Fe [5]. These synthetic chelates are agronomically efficient and generally
72 persistent in the environment [6-7], thus presenting environmental risks [8].
73 Consequently, there is considerable interest now in finding new degradable iron chelates
74 that are effective but have a lesser environmental impact than traditional synthetic
75 chelates [9-10].

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77 This study focused on a potential new iron chelate, based on the benzeneacetic acid, 2-
78 hydroxy- α -[(2-hydroxyethyl)amino] (BHH) chelating agent (for its structure and main
79 physicochemical properties, see **Fig. 1A**), whose Fe-chelated content in commercial

80 formulations may reach 8 % (w/w). The ligand has a secondary amine, two hydroxyl
81 groups – one of them phenolic, the other carboxyl – and one chiral carbon, thus it may
82 occur as two possible isomers S and R. Its structure can be compared with the chelating
83 agent *o,o*-EDDHA (**Fig. 1B**), which presents two secondary amines and two chiral
84 carbons. While *o,o*-EDDHA forms hexadentate complexes, BHH has lower coordination,
85 allowing an open structure of the chelate and making the Fe-chelate union more
86 accessible. Its stability is expected to be lower, and it will gradually degrade, providing
87 iron to the plant, as a sustainable chelating agent for use as a ferric chelate. Its
88 effectiveness in agronomic conditions is expected to be comparable to *o,o*-EDDHA due
89 to their structural similarity.

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91 Liquid chromatography (LC) using C₁₈ [11-21]- based analytical columns is the technique
92 of choice for determining iron chelates in solution or commercial products, in view of the
93 existing literature and European legislation on the use of iron chelates as fertilisers, as
94 indicated by the European Committee for Standardization (CEN). Moreover, in recent
95 years, the coupling of LC with mass spectrometry (MS) [14,20], especially tandem mass
96 spectrometry (MS/MS) using the electrospray (ESI) source in negative mode ionisation
97 in most cases [17-21] and atmospheric pressure chemical ionisation in some studies [13-
98 14], has become one of the preferred analytical techniques for analysing metal-chelator
99 complexes [13,17-18,20-21] due to its sensitivity and selectivity. Nonetheless, diode
100 array detectors (DAD) have been employed extensively in many studies [11-12, 15-16,
101 20] and routine laboratories because it is an affordable and reliable detector and achieves
102 good chromatographic separation.

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104 The aim of this study was to propose for the first time a specific analytical methodology
105 to quantify BHH/Fe³⁺ by means of LC-DAD and confirmed by LC-MS/MS. Retention
106 and separation using hydrophilic interaction liquid chromatography (HILIC) and reverse
107 phase liquid chromatography (RPLC) were compared.

108 It was consequently determined that separation would be carried out using a LiChrospher
109 RP 18. The effects of various parameters were studied, such as mobile phase composition,
110 pH, the type of organic modifier, the influence of addition of different additives and flow
111 rate. A further goal of the present study was to perform a complete validation of the
112 proposed method to determine BHH/Fe³⁺ in the potential commercial product.

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114 **2. Material and methods**

115 **2.1.Reagents**

116 Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and iron (III) nitrate nonahydrate (Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O) were
117 obtained from Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany) and hydrochloric acid (HCl) from
118 PanReac (Barcelona, Spain). LC grade ethanol (EtOH), methanol (MeOH), n-hexane and
119 acetonitrile (ACN) were supplied by Scharlau Chemie S.A. (Barcelona, Spain). Formic
120 acid, acetic acid, boric acid, ammonium formate, ammonium acetate, sodium formate,
121 ammonium monobasic dihydrogen phosphate, ammonium dibasic monohydrogen
122 phosphate, ammonium bicarbonate, trisodium citrate, sodium borate, diethylamine
123 (DEA), triethylamine (TEA), 2-Amino-2-hydroxymethyl-propane-1,3-diol (TRIS) and 2-
124 (N-morpholino)ethanesulfonic acid (MES) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich Chemie
125 GmbH (Steinheim, Germany). Ammonium hydroxide (NH₄OH) was purchased from
126 Scharlau Chemie S.A. (Barcelona, Spain). Tetrabutylammonium hydroxide (40 %
127 solution in water) was supplied by Sigma-Aldrich (Darmstadt, Germany). All the
128 chemicals used were of analytical grade. Syringe filters (17 mm, nylon 0.45 μm) were

129 purchased from Labbox Labware S.L. (Barcelona, Spain) and ultrapure water was
130 obtained using Millipore Milli-RO plus and Milli-Q systems (Bedford, MA, USA).

131 **2.2.Standard solutions**

132 The standard chelating agent benzeneacetic acid, 2-hydroxy- α -[(2-hydroxyethyl)amino]
133 (BHH) and a sample prototype of BHH/Fe³⁺ were obtained as in [22]. The titrimetric
134 purity of the chelating agent determined using a photometric method [4] was 84.6 \pm 0.5 %.

135 Briefly, about 1.10⁻⁴ M ligand solution was titrated with a 4.48 10⁻⁴ M Fe(III) standard
136 solution (Fe(NO₃)₃ in HNO₃ 0.5 mol/L) provided by Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany)
137 until absorbance at 480 nm presented no changes. Titration was carried out at 25.0 \pm 0.5
138 °C in a sealed, water-jacked glass vessel and in purified N₂ atmosphere, and iron was
139 added with a 721 NET Titrino potentiometric titrator (Metrohm AG, Herisau,
140 Switzerland). Ionic strength was maintained at 0.1 M with NaCl, and pH was fixed at 6.0
141 with 2 mM MES controlled by a pH-Stat system (Metrohm AG, Herisau, Switzerland).

142 To prepare BHH/Fe³⁺ standard solution, the ligand was dissolved in NaOH
143 (ligand:NaOH, 1:3 molar ratio). An amount of Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O, calculated to be 5 % in
144 excess of the molar amount of the ligand, was added while keeping the solution pH in the
145 range of 6-8 with NaOH or HCl. The solution pH was adjusted to 8.0 at the end of the ion
146 addition and left to stand overnight to allow excess Fe to precipitate as oxyhydroxides. It
147 was then filtered through 0.45 μ m Millipore cellulose membrane and made up to volume
148 with water. The Fe concentration in the final solution was assessed by atomic absorption
149 spectrophotometry. This solution was diluted as required.

150 A solution of the sample prototype (100 mg L⁻¹ Fe) was prepared by dissolving the
151 formulation (8 % Fe) in water and filtering it through 0.45 μ m Millipore cellulose
152 membrane prior to LC analysis. Light exposure was avoided during preparation and
153 storage due to the potential photodecomposition of chelates [23].

2.3. Chromatography Systems

HPLC-DAD

Chromatographic analyses were performed on a 1260 Infinity HPLC system (Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany). The system consisted of an online vacuum degasser, a quaternary pump and a UV-Vis detector with variable wavelengths. Agilent ChemStation software was used for system control and data acquisition. Different analytical columns used for HPLC studies were tested: RPLC columns Symmetry C₁₈ (150 x 3.9 mm; particle size 5 μm) and Spherisorb ODS2 C₁₈ (250 x 4.6 mm; particle size 5 μm) from Waters (Milford MA, USA), and LiChrospher RP-18 (150 x 4.6 mm; particle size 5 μm) and a HILIC column, SeQuant ZIC-HILIC (150 x 3.9 mm; particle size 5 μm), purchased from Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany).

After several optimisation studies, the LiChrospher RP-18 was chosen as the preferred option due to its better chromatographic performance with the iron chelate investigated. The mobile phase selected was composed of a mixture of sodium borate buffer 0.20 mM (pH=10.0) adjusted with NH₄OH (1 %, v/v) and acetonitrile (70:30, v/v) applied at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min in isocratic mode. Injection volume was set at 10 μL. Finally, measurements were performed at a wavelength of 250 nm after previously examining the corresponding UV-VIS spectra in a spectrophotometer (**Fig. S1-A**).

UHPLC-MS/MS

A UHPLC system (ACQUITY, Waters, Milford, MA, USA) and a QTOF mass spectrometer (maXis impact, Bruker Daltonik GmbH, Bremen Germany) were coupled through an electrospray (ESI) interface. The UHPLC instrument was equipped with a vacuum degasser, a binary solvent pump, an autosampler and a thermostatted column compartment. Data were acquired and processed using software Data Analysis 4.4 and Qualitative Analysis from Bruker Daltonik. Chromatographic separation was achieved

179 with the same conditions described in the HPLC-DAD subsection. Detection conditions
180 using the electrospray (ESI) source in negative ionisation mode were set as follows:
181 capillary voltage 3400 V, drying gas (N₂) 4 L/min, drying gas (N₂) temperature 200 °C
182 and nebuliser pressure 0.4 bar. The m/z scale of the mass spectra was calibrated daily by
183 infusing an atrazine mixture. Spectra were acquired in a mass range of 50-1000 m/z. The
184 compound showed an intense [M₁-H]⁻ (precursor ion: 474.0733) to obtain product ions
185 for MS/MS, carried out using an isolation width of 5 m/z and a collision energy of 30 eV.
186 Identification was performed by means of the product ions that provided the highest
187 signals. It should be noted that the UHPLC-MS/MS system was only used for
188 confirmatory purposes.

189

190 **3. Results and discussion**

191 **3.1.Optimising LC-DAD conditions**

192 The first studies were dedicated to selecting the most suitable stationary phase to
193 determine BHH/Fe³⁺. Five different types of packing materials were tested. The
194 preliminary studies revealed that the pH of the mobile phase had to be fixed in order to
195 maintain the BHH/Fe³⁺ in the ferrated ligand. The optimal value was found at pH 8; higher
196 pH values could lead to decomplexing or hydroxylation of the ion chelate and lower pH
197 values could lead to the protonation and decomplexing of the chelate or the presence of
198 the protonated Fe³⁺ form (data not shown).

199 The main characteristics of the analytical columns supplied by the manufacturer are
200 summarised in **Table S1**.

201 One of the first packing materials assayed was the hydrophilic interaction liquid
202 chromatography (HILIC) column (SeQuant ZIC-3.5 µm HILIC 150 x 3.9 mm; Merck)
203 due to the emphasis in research of the use of this type of chromatography to separate polar

204 compounds. Several studies were carried out to evaluate the effect of mobile phase
205 composition in HILIC. Mobile phases composed of aqueous-ACN solvents and soluble
206 buffer salts are recommended as they influenced the peak quality [19]. Among the buffers
207 tested were ammonium formate (pH=7.5), ammonium acetate (pH=7.5) and ammonium
208 bicarbonate (pH=8.5). The use of ammonium salts provided suitable peak shape, however
209 after examining the UV-Vis spectra the band of the Fe-phenol bonding (around 480 nm)
210 was not observed (data not shown). This event proved that the complex breaks down and
211 that the HILIC separation mechanism was not suitable for this compound.

212 Taking into account the structural similarity that this chelate presents compared with *o,o*-
213 EDDHA/Fe³⁺, it was decided that two different C₁₈ columns used in the official methods
214 would be tested [24-25] Symmetry C₁₈ (150 x 3.9 mm; particle size 5 μm) composed of
215 a high purity base-deactivated silica and based on spherical particles and Spherisorb
216 ODS2 C₁₈ (250 x 4.6 mm; particle size 5 μm) with a reversed phase sorbent based on
217 spherical silica particles and using established chromatographic methods. As expected,
218 the results showed a loss of symmetry and irreproducible peak because the iron chelate
219 studied is stable at pH 8 and the pH of the mobile phases tested were lower (pH 6 [24]
220 and pH 3 [25]). The ionisation state of the analyte directly affects the degree of its
221 interaction with the stationary phase. At these pH levels, the analyte is ionised, more polar
222 and therefore more likely to participate through hydrogen bonding. In the reversed phase,
223 the analyte will be retained for less time in hydrophobic interactions with the stationary
224 phase, and for more time forming hydrogen bonds with the aqueous part of the mobile
225 phase compared with the neutral molecule, providing less retention of the polar analytes.
226 The pH of the mobile phase influences the interactions (hydrophobic, electrostatic, $\pi \cdots \pi$,
227 etc.) that might take place during the chromatographic separation process, so pH and ionic
228 strength were evaluated. In order to obtain shorter analysis times Symmetry C₁₈ (150 x

229 3.9 mm; particle size 5 μm) was selected for the optimisation experiments. The pH range
230 studied was 7-9, which corresponds to the optimum iron chelate pH and is within the
231 optimal pH of the column. Several experiments varying in organic solvent and
232 percentage, salts and concentration were performed (compositions with the best
233 performances in terms of peak shape are summarised in **Table S2**). When using an eluent
234 with pH lower than 8 (**Fig. 2C** and **Fig. 2E**), the UV-Vis spectrum obtained for the main
235 peak corresponded to that of the free ligand BHH (**Fig. S1B**), certainly because under
236 these conditions the iron complex breaks down. When the pH was adjusted to 8, similar
237 spectra were obtained in all cases (**Fig. 2A**, **Fig. 2B**, **Fig. 2D** and **Fig. 2F**). The saturated
238 band at 225 nm is assigned to the benzene ring of the BHH. The band around 280 nm is
239 typical of the $n\text{-}\pi^*$ transitions of C = O groups or $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ transitions of C = C groups, and
240 is ascribed to carbonyl groups or phenolate, respectively, that are present in the structure
241 of BHH [26-28]. Nevertheless, the band at 480 nm characteristic of the Fe-phenol bonding
242 was not presented, indicating that iron was released, and the complex was not observed.
243 The results obtained with sodium citrate in the mobile phase provided another type of
244 spectra. When ACN was selected as an organic modifier (**Fig. 2G**), the spectrum obtained
245 showed a new intense band around 330 nm, which may correspond to the OH in *ortho*
246 substitution or even to the alcohol-Fe interaction, while the absorbance of the band
247 corresponding to the union Fe-phenolate was low. In the case of MeOH as the organic
248 solvent (**Fig. 2H** and **Fig. 2I**), the spectra obtained were similar to the spectrum obtained
249 for BHH/ Fe^{3+} standard solution in a spectrophotometer (**Fig. S1A**). Under these
250 chromatographic conditions a band shift at 440 nm was identified, suggesting that the
251 chelate structure was being modified. This effect can be explained by the complexing
252 capacity of sodium citrate. A competition between ligand BHH and citrate for Fe^{3+} may
253 take place, forming an iron-citrate complex [28] or a Fe-citrate-BHH chelate. Therefore,

254 the solvent conditions strongly affected the Fe-complexation during separation. The
255 obtained results were not adequate since in all cases the characteristic band at 480 nm of
256 the Fe-phenolate was not observed, and other unknown peaks also appeared, suggesting
257 that the complex broke down or transformed and was therefore not retained.

258 Thus, it was decided that another packing material would be tested, Luna C₁₈ (150 x
259 3.9 mm; particle size 5 µm), based on porous silica, which has a high surface
260 concentration of silanol groups and spherical particles. In this case, the retention of the
261 iron complex was achieved, providing a single peak with the band at 480 nm, but most of
262 the mobile phase tested provided an excessive peak tailing and very short retention times
263 in all cases (data not shown). It should be noted that this column is suitable for
264 hydrophobic compounds even though it is not suitable for analyte. It was studied in order
265 to compare different packaging materials.

266 Finally, the chromatography behaviour of LiChrospher RP-18 (150 x 4.6 mm; particle
267 size 5 µm) was studied. This column is made from another type of silica (silica A) with a
268 high number of unprotected silanol groups and adequate for retention of weakly basic
269 compounds. In order to optimise the organic solvent and its percentage, several
270 experiments were conducted with diverse mobile phases composed of aqueous mixtures
271 of MeOH and ACN. The best results in terms of resolution and analysis time were
272 obtained with mixture ACN:H₂O (30:70, v/v). However, peak tailing and pH shifts were
273 observed, so additives were tested to solve it. Different experiments (**Fig. 3**) were
274 performed maintaining the ratio (30:70, v/v) with different bases (DEA, EDA and TEA)
275 and salts (ammonium bicarbonate, ammonium phosphate and sodium borate buffers).
276 Successful retention of the complex was achieved in all tests, confirmed by the band at
277 480 nm. The main difference in this column was the amount of unprotected silanol groups
278 facilitating retention. The highest peak area (**Fig. 3**) was obtained with sodium borate

279 buffer pH=10 adjusted with NH₄OH 1 % (v/v). The influence of concentration (0.1-10
280 mM) on the separation was studied, and a decrease in peak area was observed when the
281 concentration increased to 0.5 mM. Thus 0.2 mM was selected as the optimal sodium
282 borate buffer concentration (see **Fig. S2**).

283 The possibility of enhancing the sensitivity (LOD/LOQ) of the method by injecting larger
284 sample volumes (5-20 μL) was considered. The results showed an increase in the signal-
285 to-noise (S/N) ratio when up to 10 μL was injected, above which S/N did not significantly
286 improve and a loss of peak symmetry was evident. Thus, 10 μL was selected as the
287 injection volume. Under the chromatography conditions described above, it was possible
288 to analyse BHH/Fe³⁺ in commercial samples by LC-DAD with an overall run time of 3.5
289 min (See **Fig. 4**).

290 **3.2.MS/MS confirmation**

291 To optimise the MS signal, 2 mg L⁻¹ solution of BHH/Fe³⁺ were directly injected using a
292 Hamilton syringe and a syringe pump with a flow rate of 3 μL min⁻¹ operated in positive
293 and negative ion modes. Optimal parameter values included negative polarity, capillary
294 voltage of 3400 V, nebuliser pressure of 0.4 bar, drying gas (N₂) flow of 4 L min⁻¹ and a
295 temperature of 200 °C. **Figure 5** shows a comparison of the full-scan spectra of a standard
296 solution prepared in the laboratory (**Fig. 5A**) and a commercial sample (**Fig. 5B**). The
297 same signals were obtained in both spectra, showing an intense [M-H]⁻ (precursor ion)
298 corresponding to the molecular ions with the general formula [mL+nFe³⁺-(3n+1)H]⁻,
299 where *L* is the chelating agent (BHH) and *n* is the number of bonded irons [31]. In order
300 to determine the stoichiometry of complexes (n iron: m chelating agent ratio) from the
301 m/z, the characteristic Fe isotopic pattern (⁵⁴Fe:⁵⁶Fe:⁵⁹Fe; 5.9:91.7:2.1), mass exact and
302 significant fragments (product ions formed by the loss of some neutral molecules)
303 obtained from the precursor ion in MRM mode to confirm their presence were used. The

304 most representative ion was m/z 474 $[2\text{BHH}+\text{Fe}^{3+}-4\text{H}^+]$, as seen by the isotopic pattern
305 ligand forming a 1:2 ($\text{Fe}^{3+}:\text{BHH}$) complex, and the transition m/z 474 \rightarrow 264,
306 corresponding to a loss of a ligand molecule ($\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{NO}_4$), was used for quantification
307 (complex 1:1). By means of MS/MS data, the ions at m/z 430 and 210 were identified as
308 product ions and corresponded with the loss of carboxylate group (CO_2) from the parent
309 and ligand BHH respectively (ESI-MS/MS spectra and proposed fragmentation pathway
310 are shown in **Supplementary Information, Fig. S3**). The synthesis of phenolate-bearing
311 polyaminocarboxylate ligands such as BHH normally lead to the formation of
312 polycondensates of high molecular weight and other by-products [26]. The analysis of
313 mass spectra revealed a condensation product at m/z 830, which was identified as a
314 bromide adduct ion $[\text{M}_2-\text{HBr}]^-$, and its fragmentation revealed the presence of the
315 complex that can bind three irons following a mono decarboxylation group and loss of
316 water, giving m/z 747 $[3\text{BHH}:3\text{Fe}^{3+}-10\text{H}^+-\text{CO}-\text{H}_2\text{O}]^-$. The isotopic pattern of molecular
317 ion at m/z 747 (100 %) and m/z 745 (19.4 %) with the calculated values 100 % and 17.7
318 % confirmed that the signal at m/z 747 could be ascribed to the 3:3 stoichiometry and its
319 confirmation ions at m/z 612 (loss of $2\text{CO}_2+\text{H}_2\text{O}+\text{C}_2\text{H}_4$) and m/z 527 $[2\text{BHH}:2\text{Fe}^{3+}-7\text{H}]^-$.
320 Free ligand (BHH) was also observed at m/z 210. Quantification and confirmation
321 transitions are shown in **Table 1**. Other signals observed in the spectra did not present
322 iron isotopic patterns and were not studied further.

323

324 **3.3.Method validation**

325 The method validation was based on the Eurachem Guide [29] determining the limits of
326 detection and quantification, linearity, precision and robustness.

327 *Limits of detection and quantification*

328 LOD and LOQ were experimentally determined by measuring the magnitude of the
329 background analytical response at the elution time of BHH/Fe³⁺. LOD and LOQ were
330 estimated as three and ten times the signal-to-noise ratio respectively and were therefore
331 0.80 ± 0.046 and 2.7 ± 0.041 mg L⁻¹ Fe respectively. It should be noted that the limits
332 obtained with the proposed method (DAD) were worse than those obtained for LC-
333 MS/MS, but they were very useful if attention was paid to the expected concentration
334 (50-100 mg L⁻¹ Fe). The use of DAD could be considered a cheap alternative to determine
335 this iron chelate with a high degree of sensitivity and, in the authors' opinion, it is not
336 necessary to use MS/MS detectors for quantification purposes when high concentrations
337 are expected, as in the determination of Fe chelated in fertilisers.

338 *Linearity studies*

339 Working solutions used to construct the calibration curve were prepared using standard
340 solution over a concentration range of LOQ up to 50 mg L⁻¹ Fe (LOQ calibration levels:
341 5, 10, 25, 50 mg L⁻¹ Fe). Calibration curves were constructed by plotting the signal on
342 the y-axis (analyte peak areas) against the analyte concentration on the x-axis, and were
343 based on six replicates of each standard solution. The graphs obtained in all the calibration
344 curves were straight lines, with linearity across the different concentration ranges studied,
345 while the coefficient of the determination values (R^2) was above 0.999 (see **Table 2**).

346 *Precision*

347 The precision of the method was evaluated as repeatability (intra-day, on the same day
348 n=6) and intermediate precision (inter-day, over three consecutive days n=6) as the
349 percentage of relative standard deviation (%RSD) at the three concentrations selected
350 (LOQ, 10, 50 mg L⁻¹ Fe). Precision was always below 5 % (**Table S3**). These results
351 indicated that the proposed method was precise in accordance with existing norms
352 (%RSD ≤ 20 %).

353 *Robustness*

354 The robustness tests were performed to determine the effects presenting small changes in
355 the method parameters as organic mobile phase composition (30 ± 0.5 % ACN), pH
356 (10 ± 0.5), buffer concentration (0.2 ± 0.05 mM), flow rate (1 ± 0.05 mL min⁻¹) and detector
357 wavelength (250 ± 0.5 nm). The calculated results, which are given in **Table S4**, show the
358 robustness of the procedure. The slight changes in the experimental parameters mentioned
359 had no significant effect, confirming the robustness of the method. The storage stability
360 of standard solutions was studied over two weeks at different temperatures (-80 °C, -20
361 °C, 4 °C and room temperature) protected from the light. The results are given in **Table**
362 **S5**. As can be seen, the compound was stable for a short storage time and storage under
363 refrigeration conditions was advisable. Nevertheless, during a long storage time, a strong
364 degradation of the compound was observed. This was more pronounced at room
365 temperature. Therefore, it is recommended that fresh solutions be prepared daily or stored
366 for short periods before analysis by HPLC-DAD.

367

368 **3.4.Application of the method**

369 The validated method was applied to determine BHH/Fe³ in a prototype fertiliser and
370 provided quite similar chromatograms and mass spectra to a standard solution, although
371 some minor differences in ion intensity were observed. Two signals corresponding to the
372 condensation products were detected and identified. No chromatographic interferences
373 were observed at the elution time of the compound in the commercial sample analysed.
374 The retention times agreed with those previously obtained from the standard solution.
375 The soluble Fe content was measured after digestion, as indicated by EC Regulations
376 2003/2003 and 1009/2019. The amount of chelated iron in the commercial product was
377 7.81 %. Since the soluble iron in this product was 8 %, the chelated fraction (chelated

378 iron respect soluble iron) was 98 %. These data are in good agreement with the
379 requirements of the regulations cited above where the chelated fraction must be at least
380 80 %.

381

382 **4. Conclusions**

383 This is the first time that an LC-DAD routine method has been developed to determine iron
384 chelated in commercial fertilisers containing BHH as the chelating agent for use as a remedy
385 for iron chlorosis in calcareous soils. The usefulness of LiChrospher RP-18 was also
386 demonstrated in a comparison with other conventional packing materials. The polar
387 modifier, mobile phase constitution and pH were optimised. The proposed method was fully
388 validated and very good analytical results were obtained, including limit of quantification, a
389 wide range of concentrations, good precision and robustness. The developed method could
390 be used to quantify commercial chelates according to the directives regulating this type of
391 product. Moreover, quantification and confirmation transitions were determined by MS/MS
392 and this could be used for further investigations of the dissipation and potential degradation
393 of iron chelate in soil.

394

395

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405 **Conflict of interest statement**

406 The authors of this manuscript declare no conflict of interest.

407

408 **Abbreviations:**

409 **DEA:** diethanolamine, **EDA:** ethanoldiamine, **HILIC:** hydrophilic interaction liquid
410 chromatography, **MRM:** multiple reaction monitoring, **QC:** quality control, **TEA:**
411 triethanolamine, **UHPLC:** ultra high performance liquid chromatography.

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518 **Figure captions**

519

520 **Figure 1 A)** Chemical structure and main physicochemical properties of BHH
521 ($C_{10}H_{13}NO_4$; molecular weight, 211.21). **B)** Chemical structure of *o,o*-EDDHA
522 ($C_{18}H_{20}N_2O_6$; molecular weight, 360.37). *Denotes asymmetric carbons.

523

524 **Figure 2** UV-Vis spectra obtained for the main peak after testing the following mobile
525 phases: **A:** ACN: H₂O (phosphate buffer 10 mM pH=8), 10:90, v/v; **B:** ACN: H₂O (Borate
526 buffer 10 mM pH=8), 10:90, v/v; **C:** ACN: H₂O (ammonium acetate 20 mM pH=7),
527 10:90, v/v; **D:** ACN: H₂O (ammonium bicarbonate 10 mM pH=8), 10:90, v/v; **E:** ACN:
528 H₂O (sodium formate 10 mM pH=7.5), 10:90, v/v; **F:** ACN: H₂O (Tris-HCl 10 mM
529 pH=8)10:90, v/v; **G:** ACN: H₂O (trisodium citrate 10 mM pH=8), 5:95, v/v; **H:** MeOH:
530 H₂O (trisodium citrate 10 mM pH=8), 5:95, v/v; **I:** MeOH: H₂O (trisodium citrate 50 mM
531 pH=8), 5:95, v/v

532

533 **Figure 3** Peak area obtained after testing the different mobile phases based on ACN:
534 aqueous solvent (30:70, v/v) at the medium QC (10 mg L⁻¹ Fe).

535

536 **Figure 4** Representative LC-DAD chromatogram and UV-VIS spectra obtained at
537 250 nm from: (A) a standard solution of BHH/Fe³⁺ at QC₂ (10 mg L⁻¹ Fe), (B) a
538 commercial sample (10 mg L⁻¹ Fe).

539

540 **Figure 5** Representative full-scan ESI-MS/MS spectra obtained by direct injection of:
541 (A) a standard solution (100 µg/L Fe) of BHH/Fe³⁺, (B) a commercial sample (100 µg L⁻¹
542 ¹ Fe).

543 **Figure 1A**

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PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

Parameter	Value
Molecular weight	211.21 g/mol
Boiling point	449 ± 40 °C
Density	1.359 ± 0.06 g/cm ³ (20 °C)

546

547 **Figure 1B**

548

PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

Parameter	Value
Molecular weight	360.37 g/mol
Boiling point	620 ± 55 °C
Density	1.417 ± 0.06 g/cm ³ (20 °C)

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550 Figure 2

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553 **Figure 3**

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579 **Table 1** Characterisation of BHH/Fe³⁺ using UHPLC-MS/MS in negative ion mode.

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Precursor ion	Product ion (CE, eV)	Measured m/z [M-H]⁻	Predicted m/z [M-H]⁻	Error (ppm)	Molecular formula	Proposed product ion
474.07	210.07(25) ^q	210.0773	210.0772	-0.1	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ NO ₄	[BHH] ⁻
	263.99(25) ^Q	263.9957	263.9965	3.1	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ FeNO ₄	[BHH:Fe ³⁺ -4H ⁺] ⁻
	430.08(25) ^q	430.0832	430.0833	0.2	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ FeN ₂ O ₆	[2BHH:Fe ³⁺ -4H ⁺ -CO ₂] ⁻
823.00	527.99(30) ^q	527.9926	527.9924	-0.3	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ Fe ₂ N ₂ O ₈	[2BHH:2Fe ³⁺ -7H] ⁻
	612.96(30) ^q	612.9696	612.9691	-0.5	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ Fe ₃ N ₃ O ₅	[3BHH:3Fe ³⁺ -10H ⁺ -CO-2H ₂ O-C ₂ H ₄ -2 CO ₂] ⁻
	746.99(30) ^Q	746.9912	746.9907	-0.5	C ₂₉ H ₂₉ Fe ₃ N ₃ O ₁₀	[3BHH:3Fe ³⁺ -10H ⁺ -CO-H ₂ O] ⁻

581

582 ^Q product ion used for quantification; ^q product ion used for confirmation

583

584

585 **Table 2** Calibration curve data (n=6), LOD and LOQ values.

Linearity range (mg/L)	Slope confidence interval \pmSD	R²	LOD\pmSD (mg/L)	LOQ\pmSD (mg/L)
2.7-50	40 \pm 0.51	0.9999	0.80 \pm 0.046	2.7 \pm 0.041

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